

Assessing the Impact of the CARES Act on Online Students: A Case Study of Two-Year Public College

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The COVID-19 pandemic has made a major impact on higher education and affected students' livelihoods and attainment of education. To help students during these challenging times the Federal CARES Act was established to provide financial relief and support students in their time of need. However, not all students are eligible to participate and these limitations have impacted funding to specific institutions. The following research study examined the implications of the CARES Act for higher education by assessing the current factors associated with the national funding model. Additionally, three additional models were created to estimate the FTE impact and approximated the financial implications of the Act in relation to the unserved or excluded populations. A survey was conducted to understand current student essential needs and the implications of COVID-19 on their livelihoods. The survey was reverse engineered to understand enrollment patterns to determine the proportionality of needs based on the enrollment patterns.

Keywords— COVID-19, high education, CARES Act, financial impact, student needs, data modeling

I. INTRODUCTION

The CARES Act is for higher education is focused on supporting students and institutions through the provision of financial assistance which is based on a specific set of data parameters found in national level public data. While the focus of the Act is to support students in need there are certain populations that are excluded and may have similar needs as the students being included and eligible for the funding. The purpose of the model development was to better understand the equity implications of the CARES Award distribution on a two-year public college in Southern California students that were excluded from the CARES Act award calculation. In addition, the student population at the college were surveyed to better understand their essential need and tied these needs back to their current enrollment patterns.

II. MODEL DEVELOPMENT

CARES data methodology utilizes full-time equivalent (FTE) unduplicated students that received Pell grants in 2018-19 financial aid year (Fall 2018, Spring 2019, & Summer 2019) and non-Pell grant students that are degree, certificate, or transfer-seeking. This model excludes any students who enrolled fully online during the fall 2018 term. The CARES calculation was based on a 75/25 split of Pell grant FTE (75%) and non-Pell grant degree, certificate, or transfer-seeking FTE (25%). The following research explored four different models to measure the impact on students and provides an estimated financial impacted associated with the CARES Act funding

model. Model 1 was based on the standards as outlined by the DOE and excluded non-credit, extended learning, incarcerated, and 100% online students. Model 2 was based on the standards as outlined by the DOE but includes 100% online state-funded students. Model 3 was based on the standards as outlined by the DOE but includes non-credit, extended learning and 100% online state-funded students. Model 4 was based on the standards as outlined by the DOE but includes all students. The following report provides the technical analysis of Models 1, 2, 3, and 4. Visual representations of the models will be included in the Appendix A.

Model 1: Federal Data Model (Baseline)

The local model data was collected on April 11, 2020 from the student information system using Argos reporting writer application for student enrollment data and the Argos data blocks to collect financial aid data. The data excluded non-credit, incarcerated, extended learning students. To control for duplication, full-time students were accounted for once using a ranking algorithm which would exclude students marked as full-time form being included in the part-time data. To control for duplication in the student educational goal, the goals of degree/certificate/transfer seeking were flagged using a ranking algorithm for the student across the whole year and disregarded previous goals if they were not within that category. To control for duplication in students receiving Pell grants, the students that has received a Pell grant once during the year were included in the Pell calculation. To calculate FTE, the number of unduplicated part-time students for the year was multiplied by 0.3333 (1/3) based on the IPEDS process. Following the DOE methodology, all students were removed from the model if they had enrolled 100% online during the fall 2018 term.

In 2018-19 Financial Aid year there were 1,754 unduplicated students that received Pell Grants. Of the 1,754 students, 761 students were enrolled 100% online in fall 2018, thus leaving 993 students. Of the 993 students, 503 were full-time (FT) students and 490 part-time (PT) students. Therefore, the calculation of FTE for students that received Pell grants would be $503 \text{ FT} + 163.32 \text{ PT} (490 * 0.3333) = 666.32 \text{ FTE}$.

In 2018-19 Financial Aid Year there were 13,349 unduplicated students that did not receive Pell grants. Of the 13,349 students, 4,273 students were enrolled 100% online in fall 2018, thus leaving 9,076 students. Of the 9,076 students, 5,827 students were degree, certificate, or transfer-seeking. Of the 5,827 students, 363 were full-time (FT) students and 5,464 were part-time (PT) students. Therefore, the calculation of FTE for students that did not received a Pell grant would be $363 \text{ FT} + 1,821.15 \text{ PT} (5,464 * 0.3333) = 2,184.15 \text{ FTE}$.

The total tabulation of the data would be 666.32 Pell grant FTE and 2,184.15 non-Pell grant degree, certificate, or transfer-seeking FTE to equal a total of 2,850.47 FTE.

Summary of Model 1

Pell Recipients: During the 2018-19 financial aid year Coastline had 15,103 unduplicated students. Of the students, 11.61% (1,754) received a Pell grant at least once during that year. In fall 2018, 56.61% (993) of students were not only enrolled in online courses. Of the 993, 50.65% (503) of students were enrolled in full-time at least once during the year.

Non-Pell Recipients: During the 2018-19 financial aid year Coastline had 15,103 unduplicated students. Of the students, 88.39% (13,349) did not receive a Pell grant at least once during that year. In fall 2018, 67.99% (9,076) of students were not only enrolled in online courses. Of the 9,076, 64.20% (5,827) of students were degree, certificate, or transfer-seeking. Of the 5,827, 6.23% (363) enrolled in full-time at least once during the year.

Calculation for FTE: The calculation is the total full-time students + 1/3 of the part-time students.

Pell Recipients 503 (Full-time) + 163.32 (Part-time) = 666.32
Non-Pell Recipients 363 (Full-time) + 1,821.15 (Part-time) = 2,184.15

Allocation Model: \$634,209

Based on the FTE calculation it would estimate the following:
Pell grant recipients: \$713.8563 per FTE x 666.32 FTE = \$475,656.75

Non-Pell grant recipients: \$72.5922 per FTE x 2,184.15 FTE = \$158,552.25

Model 2: Federal Regulations + Online

The local model data was collected on April 11, 2020 from the student information system using Argos reporting writer application for student enrollment data and the Argos data blocks to collect financial aid data. The data included state-funded and state-funded online students. To control for duplication, full-time students were accounted for once using a ranking algorithm which would exclude students marked as full-time from being included in the part-time data. To control for duplication in the student educational goal, the goals of degree/certificate/transfer seeking were flagged using a ranking algorithm for the student across the whole year and disregarded previous goals if they were not within that category. To control for duplication in students receiving Pell grants, the students that has received a Pell grant once during the year were included in the Pell calculation. To calculate FTE, the number of unduplicated part-time students for the year was multiplied by 0.3333 (1/3) based on the IPEDS process.

In 2018-19 Financial Aid Year there were 1,754 unduplicated students that received Pell Grants. Of the 1,754 students, 864 were full-time (FT) students and 890 part-time (PT) students. Therefore, the calculation of FTE for students that received Pell grants would be 864 FT + 296.64 PT (890 * 0.3333) = 1,160.64 FTE.

In 2018-19 Financial Aid Year there were 13,349 unduplicated students that did not receive Pell grants. Of the 13,349 students, 8,935 students were degree, certificate, or transfer-seeking. Of the 8,935 students, 664 were full-time (FT) students and 8,271 were part-time (PT) students. Therefore, the calculation of FTE for students that did not receive a Pell grant would be 664 FT + 2,756.72 PT (8,271 * 0.3333) = 3,420.72 FTE.

The total tabulation of the data would be 1,160.64 Pell grant FTE and 3,420.72 non-Pell grant degree, certificate, or transfer-seeking FTE to equal a total of 4,581.36 FTE.

Summary of Model 2

Pell Recipients: During the 2018-19 financial aid year Coastline had 15,103 unduplicated students. Of the students, 11.61% (1,754) received a Pell grant at least once during that year. Of the 1,754, 49.26% (864) of students were enrolled in full-time at least once during the year.

Non-Pell Recipients: During the 2018-19 financial aid year Coastline had 15,103 unduplicated students. Of the students, 88.39% (13,349) did not receive a Pell grant at least once during that year. Of the 13,349, 66.93% (8,935) of students were degree, certificate, or transfer-seeking. Of the 8,935, 7.43% (664) enrolled in full-time at least once during the year.

Calculation for FTE: The calculation is the total full-time students + 1/3 of the part-time students.

Pell Recipients: 864 (Full-time) + 296.64 (Part-time) = 1,160.64

Non-Pell Recipients: 664 (Full-time) + 2,756.72 (Part-time) = 3,420.72

Allocation Model: \$1,076,847.77

Based on the FTE calculation it would estimate the following:
Pell grant recipients: \$713.8563 x 1,443.62 FTE = \$828,530.18
Non-Pell grant recipients: \$72.5922 x 5,790.86 FTE = \$248,317.5

Model 3: Federal Regulations + Online + Non-Credit

The local model data was collected on April 11, 2020 from the student information system using Argos reporting writer application for student enrollment data and the Argos data blocks to collect financial aid data. The data included state-funded, non-credit, online, and extended learning students. To control for duplication, full-time students were accounted for once using a ranking algorithm which would exclude students marked as full-time from being included in the part-time data. To control for duplication in the student educational goal, the goals of degree/certificate/transfer seeking were flagged using a ranking algorithm for the student across the whole year and disregarded previous goals if they were not within that category. To control for duplication in students receiving Pell grants, the students that has received a Pell grant once during the year were included in the Pell calculation. To calculate FTE, the number of unduplicated part-time students for the year was multiplied by 0.3333 (1/3) based on the IPEDS process.

In 2018-19 Financial Aid Year there were 2,335 unduplicated students that received Pell Grants. Of the 2,335 students, 998 were full-time (FT) students and 1,337 part-time (PT) students. Therefore, the calculation of FTE for students that received Pell grants would be 998 FT + 445.62 PT (1,337 * 0.3333) = 1,443.62 FTE.

In 2018-19 Financial Aid Year there were 17,124 unduplicated students that did not receive Pell grants. Of the 17,124 students, 11,201 students were degree, certificate, or transfer-seeking. Of the 11,201 students, 792 were full-time (FT) students and 10,409 were part-time (PT) students. Therefore, the calculation of FTE for students that did not receive a Pell grant would be 792 FT + 3,469.32 PT (10,409

* 0.3333) = 4,261.32 FTE.

The total tabulation of the data would be 1,443.62 Pell grant FTE and 4,261.32 non-Pell grant degree, certificate, or transfer-seeking FTE to equal a total of 5,704.94 FTE.

Summary of Model 3

Pell Recipients: During the 2018-19 financial aid year Coastline had 19,459 unduplicated students. Of the students, 12.00% (2,335) received a Pell grant at least once during that year. Of the 2,335, 42.74% (998) of students were enrolled in full-time at least once during the year.

Non-Pell Recipients: During the 2018-19 financial aid year Coastline had 19,459 unduplicated students. Of the students, 87.59% (17,124) did not receive a Pell grant at least once during that year. Of the 17,124, 65.41% (11,201) of students were degree, certificate, or transfer-seeking. Of the 11,201, 7.07% (792) of students were enrolled in full-time at least once during the year.

Calculation for FTE: The calculation is the total full-time students + 1/3 of the part-time students.

Pell Recipients 998 (Full-time) + 445.62 (Part-time) = 1,443.62

Non-Pell Recipients 792 (Full-time) + 3,469.32 (Part-time) = 4,261.32

Allocation Model: \$1,339,875.80

Based on the FTE calculation it would estimate the following:

Pell grant recipients: \$713.8563 x 1,443.62 FTE = \$1,030,537.23

Non-Pell grant recipients: \$72.5922 x 4,261.32 FTE = \$309,338.57

Model 4: Federal Regulations + All Students

The local model data was collected on April 11, 2020 from the student information system using Argos reporting writer application for student enrollment data and the Argos data blocks to collect financial aid data. The data included state-funded, non-credit, incarcerated, online, and extended learning students. To control for duplication, full-time students were accounted for once using a ranking algorithm which would exclude students marked as full-time from being included in the part-time data. To control for duplication in the student educational goal, the goals of degree/certificate/transfer seeking were flagged using a ranking algorithm for the student across the whole year and disregarded previous goals if they were not within that category. To control for duplication in students receiving Pell grants, the students that has received a Pell grant once during the year were included in the Pell calculation. To calculate FTE, the number of unduplicated part-time students for the year was multiplied by 0.3333 (1/3) based on the IPEDS process.

In 2018-19 Financial Aid Year there were 2,335 unduplicated students that received Pell Grants. Of the 2,335 students, 998 were full-time (FT) students and 1,337 part-time (PT) students. Therefore, the calculation of FTE for students that received Pell grants would be 998 FT + 445.62 PT (1,337 * 0.3333) = 1,443.62 FTE.

In 2018-19 Financial Aid Year there were 22,288

unduplicated students that did not receive Pell grants. Of the 22,288 students, 15,298 students were degree, certificate, or transfer-seeking. Of the 15,298 students, 1,038 were full-time (FT) students and 14,260 were part-time (PT) students. Therefore, the calculation of FTE for students that did not receive a Pell grant would be 1,038 FT + 4,752.86 PT (14,260 * 0.3333) = 5,790.86 FTE.

The total tabulation of the data would be 1,443.62 Pell grant FTE and 5,790.86 non-Pell grant degree, certificate, or transfer-seeking FTE to equal a total of 7,234.48 FTE.

Summary of Model 4

Pell Recipients: During the 2018-19 financial aid year Coastline had 24,623 unduplicated students. Of the students, 9.48% (2,335) received a Pell grant at least once during that year. Of the 2,335, 42.74% (998) of students were enrolled in full-time at least once during the year.

Non-Pell Recipients: During the 2018-19 financial aid year Coastline had 24,623 unduplicated students. Of the students, 90.51% (22,288) did not receive a Pell grant at least once during that year. Of the 22,288, 68.64% (15,298) of students were degree, certificate, or transfer-seeking. Of the 15,298, 6.79% (1,038) of students were enrolled in full-time at least once during the year.

Calculation for FTE: The calculation is the total full-time students + 1/3 of the part-time students.

Pell Recipients 998 (Full-time) + 445.62 (Part-time) = 1,443.62

Non-Pell Recipients 1,038 (Full-time) + 4,752.86 (Part-time) = 5,790.86

Allocation Model: \$1,450,908.49

Based on the FTE calculation it would estimate the following:

Pell grant recipients: \$713.8563 x 1,443.62 FTE = \$1,030,537.23

Non-Pell grant recipients: \$72.5922 x 5,790.86 FTE = \$420,371.26

Summary of Model Findings

Pell Recipients: During the 2018-19 financial aid year Coastline had 24,623 unduplicated students. Of the students, 9.48% (2,335) received a Pell grant at least once during that year. Of the 2,335, 42.74% (998) of students were enrolled in full-time at least once during the year.

Non-Pell Recipients: During the 2018-19 financial aid year Coastline had 24,623 unduplicated students. Of the students, 90.51% (22,288) did not receive a Pell grant at least once during that year. Of the 22,288, 68.64% (15,298) of students were degree, certificate, or transfer-seeking. Of the 15,298, 6.79% (1,038) of students were enrolled in full-time at least once during the year.

Calculation for FTE: The calculation is the total full-time students + 1/3 of the part-time students.

Pell Recipients 998 (Full-time) + 445.62 (Part-time) = 1,443.62

Non-Pell Recipients 1,038 (Full-time) + 4,752.86 (Part-time) = 5,790.86

Allocation Model: \$1,450,908.49

Based on the FTE calculation it would estimate the following Pell grant recipients: \$713.8563 x 1,443.62 FTE = \$1,030,537.23

Non-Pell grant recipients: \$72.5922 x 5,790.86 FTE = \$420,371.26

Summary of Model Findings

Table 1 provides a model comparison which highlights the differences between the different models related to FTE and estimated funding.

Table 1 Model Comparison

Model	Est. FTE	Est. Funding	Difference from Model 1
Model 1 (DOE/IPEDS/Filtered Students)	2,850.47	\$634,209.00	-
Model 2 (DOE/ Including Online)	4,581.36	\$1,076,847.77	\$442,638.77
Model 3 (DOE/ Including Online, Extended Learning, and Non-Credit)	5,704.94	\$1,339,875.80	\$705,666.80
Model 4 (All Students)	7,234.48	\$1,450,908.49	\$816,699.49

The comparison shows a significant increase in FTE across the models:

- Difference between model 1 and 2 (161.72%)
- Difference between model 1 and 4 (200.14%)
- Difference between model 1 and 4 (253.80%)

The comparison shows a significant increase in funding across the models:

- Difference between model 1 and 2 (169.79%)
- Difference between model 1 and 4 (211.27%)
- Difference between model 1 and 4 (228.77%)

III. STUDENT NEEDS ASSESSMENT

During the spring 2020 semester, a COVID-19 needs assessment survey (Appendix B) was developed to understand students' essential needs during the global pandemic. The mixed methods survey was focused on the areas of household income, current housing situation, financial needs, and essential needs. The survey was sent to 8,358 students. Of the 8,358, 1,176 (14.07%) students responded to the questionnaire regarding the impact of COVID-19 and specified which essential needs they have. The sample was considered adequate based on a 95% confidence interval and margin of error of 5%. Below is a summary of the survey results.

Table 2 COVID-19 Impact on Household Income

In what ways has your household income been affected by the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic?	Percent	N
My hours at work or pay was cut	22.60%	422
A member of my family lost her/his job	20.94%	391
I lost my job	18.26%	341
My family ran out of food and/or essential items	8.84%	165
My family does not have money for food and/or essential items	8.30%	155
My hours at work were increased	5.89%	110
I had to take off work because of childcare challenges	5.25%	98
A member of my family got sick	4.55%	85
I got sick	3.86%	72
I had to get a second job	1.50%	28

Table 2 shows that 1,153 students responded to the question with 1,867 answer selections and 249 comments. The primary impact of COVID-19 on household income was loss of work hours (22.60%) and overall job loss (39.21%). The comments associated around the themes of not having money for essentials/bills, fear of being laid off, and managing work, school, and family life.

Table 3 COVID-19 Impact on Housing

How has your housing situation been affected by the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic?	Percent	N
I cannot afford to pay rent	67.82%	373
I moved in with other friends/relatives	21.82%	120
I had to move	8.00%	44
I do not have a place to live	2.36%	13

Table 3 shows that 863 responded to the question with 550 answer selections and 400 comments. The primary impact to students housing situations were related to being unable to pay rent (67.82%) and moving in with relatives or friends (21.82%). The comments were mixed with themes around being quarantined at home, not having money for rent, and having stable living situation.

Table 4 Financial Needs

What are your current financial needs?	Percent	N
Food and Supply Assistance	31.82%	413
Tuition Assistance	29.12%	378
Technology Assistance	14.87%	193
Medical Assistance	10.17%	132
Transportation Assistance	7.24%	94
Child Care Assistance	6.78%	88

Table 4 shows that 959 responded to the question with 1,298 answer selections and 217 comments. The primary needs included food and essential supplies (31.82%), tuition assistance (29.12%), and technology assistance (14.87%). The comments were mixed with themes around needing money for bills/rent (40.73%) and not having any financial needs (38.55%).

The students were asked an opened-ended question asking them to specify which essential items (e.g., food, household supplies, cash/money, motel vouchers) were in

need since COVID-19. The results of the 862 responses listed the essential needs were household supplies/sanitation items (52.32%), money (37.35%), food (29.58%), bills (10.67%). In contrast, 17.17% of respondents indicated that they did not need anything at this point.

The students were asked an opened-ended question to specify which essential learning materials, supplies, or technology are needed. There were mixed responses with many students indicating that there is a need for technology and learning materials such as internet (22.34%), laptop/desktop (20.69%), and learning materials/supplies (12.97%). In contrast 32.0% of respondents indicated that there were currently no needs for learning materials or technology.

Finally, the students were asked an open-end question to indicate any other essential needs which 461 students responded with requests that were like the previous sections. The emerging themes from the responses were also mixed with most students specifying essential needs (45.12%) around money, work, food, sanitation supplies, mental health and medical support while 39.91% indicated to not having any additional needs.

Student Needs in Relation to Instructional Modality

The survey result data was further explored by attributing student enrollment data by instructional modality by student response. The instructional modality was categorized into three areas which include students enrolled 100% in-person and hybrid (IP/H); 100% online (OL); and student enrollment across multiple instructional modalities (1+) during the spring 2020 semester. Table 5 provides a summary of the data findings.

Table 5 Student Needs by Instructional Modality

	Answers	N	IP/H	OL	1+
Financial	I got sick	70	20%	60%	20%
	A member of my family got sick	82	20%	65%	16%
	My hours at work or pay was cut	420	21%	67%	11%
	I had to get a second job	26	23%	62%	15%
	My hours at work were increased	108	12%	75%	13%
	I had to take off work because of childcare challenges	98	15%	73%	11%
	I lost my job	335	20%	63%	17%
	A member of my family lost her/his job	386	22%	64%	15%
	My family ran out of food and/or essential items	163	17%	69%	15%
	My family does not have money for food and/or essential items	155	14%	70%	16%
Housing	I cannot afford to pay rent	369	22%	62%	16%
	I had to move	41	10%	73%	17%
	I moved in with other friends/relatives	118	16%	69%	14%
	I do not have a place to live	12	33%	42%	25%

Essential Needs				
Technology Assistance	192	18%	70%	12%
Child Care Assistance	86	15%	72%	13%
Tuition Assistance	372	16%	72%	13%
Food and Supply Assistance	408	18%	68%	15%
Medical Assistance	135	17%	68%	15%
Transportation Assistance	92	18%	65%	16%

Table 5 show that most students who indicated to have financial implication related to the COVID-19 situation are enrolled 100% in online courses. Similar data trends could be attributed COVID-19 impacts on housing situations with many students being unable to afford rent. Following the trends student enrolled 100% online had the highest proportionality related to essential needs. The data shows that there is an emergence of essential needs regardless of modality which counters the framework of the CARES Act for higher education.

IV. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

While the research was able to model the implications of not including the online and other special student populations into the CARES Act funding formula, a few limitations exist. The first limitation is that the data was not retrieved from the DOE or IPEDS directly and did not account for any preexisting filters that were applied to the data. This may relate to slight difference in the outcome. The data that was modeled was based on the local data which continues to be refined in the student information systems, where IPEDS data is a static snapshot in-time. Other assumptions included that the original data model for financial implication would directly translate to the local data and thus may be underestimated since the IPEDS data has filtered or limited information. Other limitations to the survey are that it did not capture every student experience but was an adequate representation based on the sample size estimations.

Future research should be conducted on a national level to measure the impact of the model overall on online and other special student populations.

V. DISCUSSION

The research study examined the implications of the CARES Act for higher education by assessing the current factors associated with the national funding model. Additionally, three additional models were created to estimate the FTE impact and approximated the financial implications of the Act in relation to the unserved or excluded populations. A survey was conducted to understand current student essential needs and the implications of COVID-19 on their livelihoods. The survey was reverse engineered to understand enrollment patterns to determine the proportionality of needs based on the enrollment patterns. Overall, the comparison of data models in addition the student mixed methods survey finds outline there is clear evidence that online and other special student populations have been equally or potentially more impacted that the population that the CARES Act of higher education was intended to serve.

2018-19 CARES Data Model 1.0

Model Excludes: Non-Credit, Incarcerated, full online, and Extended Learning Students

2018-19 CARES Data Model 2.0

Total FTE = 4,581.36

\$1,076,847.77

Excluded: Non-Credit, Incarcerated, full online, and Extended Learning Students

2018-19 CARES Data Model 3.0

Excluded: Incarcerated Students

2018-19 CARES Data Model 4.0

Appendix B

Spring 2020 Student Needs Assessment Survey

Dear Students,

Thank you, in advance, for taking the time to answer this survey. The goal of the survey to get a better understanding of your needs during the coronavirus pandemic while you shelter in place so that we can support your continued enrollment and success. Also, we want to be able to anticipate your needs when the shelter-in place is lifted. The survey is only open for a short time, so please take a minute now to complete the survey.

1. In what ways has your household income been affected by the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic? (Select all that apply)

- I got sick
- A member of my family got sick
- My hours at work or pay was cut
- I had to get a second job
- My hours at work were increased
- I had to take off work because of childcare challenges
- I lost my job
- A member of my family lost her/his job
- My family ran out of food and/or essential items
- My family does not have money for food and/or essential items
- Other (please specify)

2. How has your housing situation been affected by the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic? (Select all that apply)

- I cannot afford to pay rent
- I had to move
- I moved in with other friends/relatives
- I do not have a place to live
- Other (please specify)

3. What are your current financial needs?

- Technology Assistance
- Child Care Assistance
- Tuition Assistance
- Food and Supply Assistance
- Medical Assistance
- Transportation Assistance
- Other (please specify)

4. What essential items (e.g., food, household supplies, cash/money, motel vouchers) are you in need of since the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic?

5. What essential learning materials, supplies, or technology are you in need of since the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic?

6. Please list any other essential needs you have.